

OCEAN ICE News – January 2026

OCEAN ICE is a Horizon Europe project, funded by the European Commission and UKRI. OCEAN ICE stands for Ocean-Cryosphere Exchanges in Antarctica: Impacts on Climate and the Earth System.

OCEAN ICE News is a monthly newsletter updating about the project's progress, results, and other exciting events! Be sure to follow us on LinkedIn to stay informed.

Welcome!

Welcome to January's edition of OCEAN ICE News. We're excited to bring you the latest updates from the OCEAN ICE community.

In this issue, you'll meet our featured researcher of the month and catch up on key activities, such as an OCEAN ICE publication, OCEAN ICE at Antarctica InSync Workshop, highlighting December's Climate Coffee. We have some upcoming Climate Coffee's that you can register for in January, February and March. Don't forget to mark your calendars for the upcoming events where OCEAN ICE will be represented.

We hope you enjoy exploring this month's updates, and we look forward to sharing more in February!

Researcher in the Spotlight: Torsten Albrecht

Check out our latest 'Researcher in the Spotlight' feature on Torsten Albrecht, a co-lead of WP6 and a lead of the Ice Dynamics theme in the Earth Resilience Science Unit (ERSU)—a new bridge group between the Potsdam Institute for Climate Impact Research (PIK) and the newly founded Max Planck Institute of Geoanthropology (MPI-GEA) in Germany.

Read the feature on Torsten [here](#).

Stay tuned for more features from our Research Team in OCEAN ICE.

Catching up on the Latest OCEAN ICE Activities

OCEAN ICE Publication: Observed large-scale and deep-reaching compound ocean state changes over the past 60 years

A newly published article in Nature Climate Change ([Nature Portfolio](#)) offers one of the most comprehensive assessments to date of how multiple climate-related stressors are reshaping the ocean.

Over the last six decades, the ocean has been undergoing not just one, but multiple simultaneous climate-driven changes. Warming, acidification, deoxygenation, and shifting salinity patterns are interacting in ways that reshape ocean conditions from the surface all the way to the deep ocean. Using a time-of-emergence approach applied across a suite of physical and biogeochemical observations, the study shows that compound climate impact-drivers are now emerging across vast regions, including the subtropical/tropical Atlantic, subtropical Pacific, Arabian Sea, and the Mediterranean.

Read the full article [here](#).

OCEAN ICE at Antarctica InSync Workshop

Antarctica InSync held a workshop at the ESA-ESRIN site in Frascati Italy over the 3rd-6th of November. This was attended by over 120 Southern Ocean, Earth Observation and Antarctic scientists from around the world, who partook in three days of intense discussions and writing to develop a coherent science plan for Antarctica InSync activities, planned for 2027-2030.

The workshop was focused on producing white papers that would outline the central science questions, activities and methodologies needed to produce synchronous and intercomparable observations of key properties around the Antarctic. These were split across the seven InSync core science themes and in each case a team of experts were tasked with producing a white paper covering: Motivations, Knowledge Gaps, and Observing Strategies. These white papers also identified the essential variables needed to deliver the identified science outcomes.

Read the full article [here](#).

OCEAN ICE Climate coffee – December

Climate Coffee with Ioannis Prapas and Haralampos Gavriilidis on Manteo AI: Making Earth Observation Workflows More Intuitive.

Working with Earth observation and remote sensing data is often a labour-intensive process. From identifying appropriate data sources and handling heterogeneous raster and vector formats to cleaning, transforming, and applying machine learning methods, each step requires significant expertise and infrastructure. These hurdles can slow scientific progress and limit the accessibility of advanced geospatial analysis.

In this talk, we present the development of Manteo AI, a system designed to lower these barriers by integrating state-of-the-art research from data systems, remote sensing, and Earth observation, as well as artificial intelligence, particularly large language models. At its core, Manteo offers an interactive “chat map” interface, allowing practitioners to explore geospatial datasets through natural language queries and receive dynamic, visual responses in the form of maps, plots, and dashboards. As part of our roadmap, we also plan a community-driven model hub for Earth observation, where domain-specific models can be shared and seamlessly integrated into workflows. We invite practitioners to share their experiences and bottlenecks, so we can explore together how such cross-disciplinary methods might support more efficient and inclusive geospatial research.

11 December 2025 | 10:00 - 10:45 CET
Online

Ioannis Prapas and Haralampos Gavriilidis
(Manteo)

Manteo AI: Making Earth Observation
Workflows More Intuitive

Danish Meteorological Institute

Funded by
the European Union

Climate Coffees

Since its relaunch the [Climate Coffee series](#) has been in full swing. If you've missed any of the recent ones, don't you worry, you may catch up [here](#).

Climate Coffee

Upcoming Events

Climate Coffee

We have an upcoming Climate Coffee in November and December, make sure you register for all of them through the link on [OCEAN ICE](#).

Climate Coffee with Fehmi Dilmahamod on Characteristics of Mesoscale-to-Submesoscale Eddies in the Labrador Sea

29 January 2026, 10:00 – 10:45 (CET)

29 January 2026 | 10:00 - 10:45 CET
Online
Fehmi Dilmahamod (GEOMAR)
Characteristics of Mesoscale-to-Submesoscale Eddies in the Labrador Sea: Insights from Ship Observations

Danish Meteorological Institute

Funded by the European Union

Climate Coffee with Linus Vogt on Increased future ocean heat uptake constrained by Antarctic sea ice extent

19 February 2026, 15:00 – 15:45 (CET)

19 February 2026 | 15:00 - 15:45 CET
Online
Linus Vogt
(NYU, Sorbonne, LOCEAN)
Increased future ocean heat uptake constrained by Antarctic sea ice extent

Danish Meteorological Institute

Funded by the European Union

Climate Coffee with Giulia Bonino on Mediterranean summer marine heatwaves triggered by weaker winds under subtropical ridges

26 March 2026, 15:00 – 15:45 (CET)

26 March 2026 | 10:00 - 10:45 CET

Online

Giulia Bonino

(Euro-Mediterranean Center on Climate Change)

**Mediterranean summer marine
heatwaves triggered by weaker winds
under subtropical ridges**

Danish Meteorological Institute

OCEAN:ICE

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the European Union

OCEAN ICE at Ocean Sciences Meeting

Members from OCEAN ICE will be presenting at the [Ocean Sciences Meeting in Glasgow, Scotland 2026](#). Please find the below talks during the meeting and look out for any future sessions/talks too:

David Chandler, Petra Langebroek, Heiko Goelzer, Michele Petrini and Morven Muilwijk.

Abstract ID: 2009920

Abstract Title: Global impacts of Greenland and Antarctic ice sheet freshwater fluxes in the Norwegian Earth System Model (NorESM)

Final Abstract Number: HE43A-09

Presentation Type: Oral

Session Number and Title: HE43A: Ice Sheet–Ocean Interactions: From Micro- to Climate-Scale II Oral

Session Date and Time: Thursday, 26 February 2026; 14:00 - 15:30 GMT

Presentation Time: 15:20 - 15:30 GMT

Location: SEC; Hall 3, Blue Horizon

Timothee Bourgeois, David Chandler, Michele Petrini, Elin Darelius, Petra Langebroek, Heiko Goelzer, and Jörg Schwinger.

Abstract ID: 2008310

Abstract Title: Committed Southern Ocean warming and implications for the Antarctic Ice Sheet following emission cessation

Presentation Type: Poster

Session Date and Time: Thursday, 26 February 2026; 16:00 - 18:00 GMT

Session Number and Title: HE44D: Variability, Circulation, and Ongoing Change in the Southern Ocean VI Poster

Location: SEC; Hall 4 (Poster Hall)

Zhetao Tan:

Changing Properties of South Atlantic Upper-Ocean Water Masses During the Past 45 Years' in session PS21A - Atlantic Ocean Connectivity Across Latitudes: Large-Scale Processes, Observations, Modeling, and Impacts, which are targeted to the OCEAN ICE topic.

Session Date and Time: Tuesday, 24 February 2026, 09:23 - 09:33

Location: Hall 1 (SEC)

Happening Soon

OCEAN ICE will be at these upcoming events. Will you also be there? Let us know!

- 13th – 15th January, [TRICUSO Annual Meeting](#), Bergen, Norway
- 20th January 2026, [PROS4SORP Webinars](#), Online
- 9th – 12th February 2026, [Open Science Conference](#), New Zealand
- 22nd – 27th February 2026, [Ocean Sciences Meeting](#), Glasgow, Scotland
- 9th – 13th March 2026, [CMIP 2026 Meeting](#), Kyoto, Japan
- 17th – 19th August 2026, [FRISP 2026](#), Kristineberg, Sweden

Do you know of any exciting events that OCEAN ICE should be a part of? Shoot us a mail at oceanice.eu@gmail.com.

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www.ocean-ice.eu

<https://www.linkedin.com/company/euoceanice/>

https://twitter.com/OCEANICE_EU

<https://fediscience.org/@OceanIceEU>

<https://www.facebook.com/OCEANICEEU/>

[OCEAN ICE \(@oceaniceeu.bsky.social\) — Bluesky](#)

Who is OCEAN ICE?

OCEAN ICE stands for Ocean-Cryosphere Exchanges in Antarctica: Impacts on Climate and the Earth System. OCEAN ICE is a Horizon Europe project, funded by the European Commission and UKRI. OCEAN ICE focus on understanding how the Antarctic ice sheet and the surrounding Southern Ocean influence our global climate

and reduce the level of uncertainty around how much the Antarctic ice sheet will melt in the coming centuries. OCEAN ICE considers the critical role of feedbacks between ocean circulation, ice sheet change and tipping points and the global climate. [Find out more](#)

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Disclaimer: Funded by the European Union. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the authors only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or European Research Executive Agency (REA). Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.